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Stability Indicating RP-HPLC Method Development and Validation for Determination of Process Related Impurities and Degradation Products of Tazarotene in Tazarotene Topical Formulation

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ABSTRACT

A simple, specific, accurate and stability-indicating reversed phase high performance liquid Chromatographic method was developed and validated for determination of related substances in Tazarotene gel. Chromatographic separation was achieved by using Waters symmetry 150 × 3.9mm, 5μ column as stationary phase while mobile phase A was buffer: organic modifier, 40:60 v/v (Buffer=10 mM KH₂PO₄ with pH 3.0 by orthophosphoric acid and organic modifier = methanol: tetra hydrofuran, 95:5 v/v) and mobile phase B as organic modifier. Method was developed in gradient mode with 55 minutes, at flow rate of 1.0 mL/min. Effluents were monitored at 325 nm. The method was validated for specificity, linearity, accuracy, precision, limit of quantification, limit of detection, robustness and solution stability. The RRF (relative response factor) values of impurity-A, impurity-B, impurity-C determined from linearity study were 0.99, 1.78 and 1.24 respectively. Limit of quantification of Tazarotene, impurity-A, impurity-B and impurity-C was found to be 0.02 μg/mL, 0.02 μg/mL, 0.01 μg/mL and 0.01 μg/mL respectively. Recovery was found to be in the range of 95-105%. The method was proved to be robust with respect to changes in flow rate, buffer pH and column temperature. The proposed method was successfully applied for the quantitative determination of related substances in Tazarotene topical formulation.

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INTRODUCTION

Tazarotene (TAZ), ethyl 6-((4,4-dimethylthiochroman-6-yl)ethynyl) nicotinate, is a member of a new generation of receptor selective, synthetic retinoid for the topical treatment of mild to moderate plaque psoriasis, acne vulgaris and photoaging. It represents an evolution of dermatology research aimed to the discovery of retinoids that are safer than tretinoin and/or are more effective in skin rejuvenation or treatment of acne and other conditions¹⁻³. Psoriasis is one of the most common human skin diseases. It is characterized by excessive growth and aberrant differentiation of corneocytes, but is fully reversible with appropriate therapy⁴.

TAZ as an oral retinoids have long been used in the treatment of psoriasis, their use has often been limited to patients with severe psoriasis, due to the potential adverse side effects associated with their use. Patients with mild-to-moderate psoriasis have to rely on topical therapies such as topical steroids, vitamin D3 analogues, coal tar and anthralin^{5,6}.

A detailed literature survey for TAZ revealed that a quantitative determination of TAZ was reported on HPTLC⁷, isolation and structural characterization also reported for impurities of TAZ¹, Stability-indicating chemometric methods reported for the determination of TAZ⁸, Stability indicating method for estimation of TAZ and its related substances determination in bulk drug by RPLC⁹, a stability-indicating spectrophotometric methods for determination of TAZ in the presence of its alkaline degradation product by derivative spectrophotometric techniques¹⁰, disposition and biotransformation of the acetylenic retinoid TAZ in humans¹¹, hydrolysis of TAZ and enzyme inhibition were assessed by monitoring the disappearance of TAZ and the appearance of its primary metabolite tazarotenic acid in blood sample by HPLC¹². To the best of our knowledge, none of the method is available for determination of three known impurities of TAZ from TAZ topical formulation. The aim of the present work was to develop and validate a method for determination of process related impurity and degradation impurity in TAZ topical formulation. Moreover, method development approach is discussed with an important of diluent selection, which was not limited to extraction and solution stability but, it was extended to understand the chemical compatibility (between drug and diluent) during forced degradation study. The drug product stability guideline Q1A (R2) issued by the International Conference on Harmonization (ICH)¹³ suggests that stress studies should be carried out on a drug to establish its inherent stability characteristics, leading to identification of degradation products and, hence, supporting the suitability of the proposed analytical procedures. It also requires that analytical procedures for testing the stability of samples should be stability-indicating and should be fully validated. Chemical structures, IUPAC name, UV spectra of all compounds are presented in Figure 1

Tazarotene; (TAZ)

Ethyl 6-((4,4-dimethylthiochroman-6-yl)ethynyl) nicotinate

Impurity-A; (Imp-A)

Methyl 6-[(4,4-dimethyl-3,4-dihydro-2H-thiochromen-6-yl)ethynyl] nicotinate

Impurity-B; (Imp-B)

Ethyl 6-[(4,4-dimethyl-1-oxido-3,4-dihydro-2H-thiochromen-6-yl)ethynyl]nicotinate

Impurity-C; (Imp-C)

6-[(4,4-dimethyl-3,4-dihydro-2H-thiochromen-6-yl)ethynyl]nicotinic acid

Figure No.1 Chemical structures, IUPAC name, individual UV spectrum of Tazartoene and related impurities

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials:

TAZ gel, placebo, TAZ working standards and impurities standards were provided by Dr. Reddy's laboratories Ltd., Hyderabad, India. HPLC grade methanol, tetrahydrofuran, acetonitrile and orthophosphoric acid were used of Rankem, India. Monobasic potassium dihydrogen phosphate GR was used of Merck, Mumbai, India. 0.45 μm membrane filter was purchased from Pall life science limited (India). 0.2 μm PVDF syringe filter was used of whatman, India. Water for HPLC was generated using Milli-Q Plus water purification system (Millipore, Milford, MA, USA).

HPLC (Alliance Waters, separation module 2695, photo diode array detector 2996, UV detector 2487 with Empower2 software. Photo-stability chamber (Sanyo, Leicestershire, UK). Dry air oven (Cintex, Mumbai, India)

Figure No.2 A typical chromatogram for gradient optimization (a) resolution between impurity-A and unknown = 1.7 (b) resolution between impurity-A and unknown = 2.3

Figure No.3 Base hydrolysis study using methanol and water (80:20 v/v) as diluent

Figure No.4 Mechanism of formation of impurity-A from TAZ through impurity-C

HPLC instrumentation and chromatographic conditions:

The LC system of Waters Alliance HPLC with PDA detector was used for this study and chromatographic separation was achieved on Waters Symmetry C18 (150 mm X 3.9 mm, 5 μ m) column as stationary phase with binary gradient mode. Gradient program was used as time (min)/mobile phase-A (%)/mobile phase-B (%); 0.0/100/00, 10/100/00, 15/75/25, 45/75/25, 47/100/00, 55/100/00. Where, mobile phase-A was Buffer : organic modifier, 40:60 v/v (v/v) and mobile phase-B, Organic modifier. Buffer was 10 mM potassium dihydrogen phosphate, pH adjusted to 3.0 with orthophosphoric acid and filtered through 0.22 μ m membrane and organic modifier was methanol : tetrahydrofuran, 95:5 v/v. Column oven temperature was maintained at 30°C and injection volume for each study preparation was 50 μ L. Eluent with flow rate of 1.0 mL/min was monitored at 325 nm with PDA detector. Acetonitrile : water, 80:20 v/v was used as a final diluent. The stress degraded samples and the solution stability samples were analyzed using a PDA detector covering the range of 200-400nm.

Diluted standard solution preparation :

Standard solution was prepared by dissolving standard substance in diluent to obtain solution containing 1 μ g/mL of TAZ.

Sample solution preparation:

An accurately weighed sample equivalent to 5 mg of TAZ was taken into 50 mL volumetric flask. About 35 mL of diluent was added to this volumetric flask and sonicated in an ultrasonic bath for 15 min with intermittent shaking, diluted to the volume with diluent, mixed well, centrifuged at 7500 rpm for 15min. Supernatant solution was filtered through 0.2 μ m PVDF syringe filter.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Method development and optimization:

Prime objective of an RP-HPLC method development for determination of related impurities in TAZ topical dosage form was: the method should be able to determine all TAZ related impurities in single run and should be

accurate, reproducible, robust and stability indicating. All degradation products from stress conditions should be well separated from each other and method should be simple to use in analytical research and quality control laboratory for routine use. The spiked solution of related compounds (Imp-A, Imp-B, Imp-C) and TAZ were used for method development to optimize chromatographic conditions and separation by RP-HPLC. All impurities were spiked in TAZ in such a way to achieve 1 µg/mL for each impurities and 100 µg/mL for TAZ. Further more primary developed method was challenged by forced degradation as a pre-validation.

Table No.1: System suitability results (Precision, Intermediate precision and Robustness)

Parameter	*Area ratio	USP tailing of TAZ	USP theoretical plates of TAZ	Relative retention time		
				Imp-A	Imp-B	Imp-C
Precision	1.02	1.1	15337	0.77	0.17	0.55
Intermediate precision	1.04	1.0	12959	0.77	0.17	0.54
At 1.2 mL/min flow rate	1.00	1.1	17883	0.79	0.16	0.58
At 0.8 mL/min flow rate	1.02	1.2	9492	0.77	0.18	0.53
At 35°C column temp.	1.01	1.2	9926	0.79	0.17	0.57
At 25°C column temp.	1.02	1.0	16812	0.77	0.17	0.53
Buffer pH 3.2	1.02	1.0	16515	0.77	0.17	0.57
Buffer pH 2.8	1.00	1.0	16552	0.77	0.17	0.51

*... Area ratio of Tazarotene peak from two replicate diluted standard injections;
USP...United state pharmacopeia

Mobile phase and gradient optimization:

A method development was started with Waters symmetry C18 150 mm x 3.9 mm, 5 µm column as stationary phase. Mobile phase A was buffer (10 mM KH₂PO₄ with pH 3.0 by orthophosphoric acid), while mobile phase B was methanol:tetra hydrofuran, 95:5 v/v. For gradient optimization first programme was time (minutes)/mobile phase B(%); 0/60,10/60,15/80,25/80,30/60,35/60 and obtained chromatogram shown in Figure 2(a), in order to achieve better chromatographic separation (between impurity-A and unknown impurity), mobile phase-B was modified as time (minutes)/mobile phase B(%); 0/60,10/60,15/70,45/70,47/60,55/60 as shown in Figure 2(b).

Finally, in order to increase the mobile phase stability (to prevent microbial growth) organic component was added to buffer of mobile phase A, in the ratio of buffer : organic modifier, 40:60 v/v.

Diluent selection:

Initially, methanol: water, 80:20 was used as diluent with consideration of solubility of TAZ and related impurities in methanol for better extraction and water was incorporated to reduce the rate of evaporation. But, during the forced degradation study (base hydrolysis), significant level of TAZ impurity-A was observed

[Figure 3], which was unusual to form from Tazarotene as a degradation product by normal degradation pathway. Further more an impurity-A was also not observed during TAZ drug product stability even up to 6M, 40°C/ 75 %RH.

In order to explain the formation of impurity-A from TAZ, hypothetical concept was that TAZ could form impurity-C which is an base hydrolysis from TAZ (i.e. Ester to acid, TAZ to impurity-C) and because of presence of excess methanol in diluent in presence of base during stress condition impurity-C was converted to impurity-A (acid to ester, impurity-C to impurity-A), a typical example of transesterification by two step mechanism as shown in Figure 4. This hypothesis was proven by replacing methanol component by acetonitrile in diluent, where reaction was limited to step-1 of hydrolysis as shown in chromatogram of Figure 6(b).

Analytical method validation:

After satisfactory development of method it was subjected to method validation as per ICH guideline¹⁴. The method was validated to demonstrate that it is suitable for its intended purpose by the standard procedure. Analytical method validation was carried out by means of system suitability, accuracy, precision, linearity, robustness, solution stability and filter compatibility.

System suitability:

The system suitability was performed by diluted standard solution and impurities spiked solution (1 µg/mL Imp-A, Imp-B, Imp-C and 100 µg/mL of TAZ). The system suitability parameters were evaluated and found to be within the limits [Table 1].

Forced degradation study:

Forced degradation was performed on Tazarotene topical formulation to achieve desired degradation and placebo as well as Tazarotene drug substance were treated with similar conditions as mentioned below, based on development trials optimized forced degradation conditions were established. Final sample concentration was achieved 100 µg/mL of Tazarotene with diluent as proposed sample concentration.

Oxidative degradation:

Tazarotene sample equivalent to 5mg of Tazarotene was taken into 50 mL volumetric flask, added 15 mL diluents and sonicated for 15minutes with intermittent swirling. Then subjected to oxidative stress condition by 5 mL of 3% v/v H₂O₂ solution in 50 mL volumetric flask and kept on room temperature for 15 min, diluted to volume with diluents. Further a portion of sample centrifuged at 7500 rpm for 15min. Supernatant solution was filtered through 0.2 µm PVDF syringe filter. Degradation in oxidative condition was achieved by 11.15 %.

Acid degradation:

Tazarotene sample equivalent to 5mg of Tazarotene was taken into 50 mL volumetric flask, added 15 mL diluent and sonicated for 15minutes with intermittent swirling. Then subjected to acid hydrolysis condition by 5 mL of 0.5N HCl solution in 50 mL volumetric flask and kept on room temperature for 15 min, sample was neutralised with 0.5N NaOH and diluted to volume with diluents. Further a portion of sample centrifuged at 7500 rpm for 15min. Supernatant solution was filtered through 0.2 µm PVDF syringe filter. Degradation in oxidative condition was achieved by 1.06 %.

Base degradation:

Tazarotene sample equivalent to 5mg of Tazarotene was taken into 50 mL volumetric flask, added 15 mL diluents and sonicated for 15minutes with intermittent swirling. Then subjected to base hydrolysis condition by 5 mL of 0.5N NaOH solution in 50 mL volumetric flask and kept on room temperature for 15 min, sample was neutralised with 0.5N HCl and diluted to volume with diluents. Further a portion of sample centrifuged at 7500 rpm for 15min. Supernatant solution was filtered through 0.2 µm PVDF syringe filter. Degradation in oxidative condition was achieved by 6.75 %.

Thermal degradation:

Tazarotene sample equivalent to 5mg of Tazarotene was taken into 50 mL volumetric flask and exposed at 60°C for 6 hours. Added 35 mL diluents and sonicated for 15minutes with intermittent swirling. Diluted to volume with diluent. Further a portion of sample centrifuged at 7500 rpm for 15min. Supernatant solution was filtered through 0.2 µm PVDF syringe filter. Degradation in oxidative condition was achieved by 0.70%.

Table No.2: Data of forced degradation study of TAZ

Degradation condition	Imp-A %	Imp-B %	Imp-C %	Unk. Max. Imp. %	Total Imps %	Drug assay %
Control sample	0.06	0.35	ND	0.02	0.43	99.9
Acid degradation (0.5N HCl RT,15min)	0.07	0.38	0.45	0.02	1.06	99.4
Base degradation (0.5N NaOH RT,15 min)	0.09	0.94	5.70	0.02	6.75	93.7
Peroxide degradation (3% H ₂ O ₂ RT,15 min)	0.02	10.87	0.05	0.16	11.15	89.3
Photo degradation (1.2 million lux hours)	0.05	7.66	0.07	0.62	8.85	91.6
Thermal degradation (60°C, 6 h)	0.09	0.59	ND	0.02	0.70	99.7
RT... Room temperature; Unk. Max Imp.... Unknown maximum impurity						

Photolytic degradation:

Tazarotene sample equivalent to 5mg of Tazarotene was taken into 50 mL volumetric flask and kept in photo stability chamber to expose it for 1.2 million lux hours. Added 35 mL diluent and sonicated for 15minutes with intermittent swirling. Diluted to volume with diluents. Further a portion of sample centrifuged at 7500 rpm for

15min. Supernatant solution was filtered through 0.2 μm PVDF syringe filter. Degradation in oxidative condition was achieved by 8.85%.

Table No.3: LOD, LOQ and RRF results of TAZ

Parameter	Imp-A ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Imp-B ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Imp-C ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	TAZ ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)
LOD	0.005	0.003	0.002	0.006
LOQ	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.02
Slope	163784.1	293877.2	205216.9	164858.8
RRF	0.99	1.78	1.24	1.00

Table No.4: Linearity of IMP-A, IMP-B, IMP-C and TAZ

Component	Linearity range ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Correlation Coefficient (r)	Y-intercept bias in %
TAZ	0.02 - 1.50	0.9992	-1.0
Imp-A	0.02 - 0.75	0.9999	0.9
Imp-B	0.01 - 4.59	1.0000	0.2
Imp-C	0.01 - 0.76	0.9999	0.7

Table No.5: Method precision data at LOQ of TAZ

Sample No.	Imp-A %	Imp-B %	Imp-C %	Total Impurities %
Average [#]	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.03
%RSD*	7.86	6.44	12.04	3.49
#... Average of six determinations; *... Determined on six values				

Table No.6: Method precision of TAZ

Sample No.	Imp-A %	Imp-B %	Imp-C %	Total Impurities %
Average [#]	0.36	0.32	0.32	1.00
%RSD*	5.42	4.62	1.28	2.44
#... Average of six determinations; *... Determined on six values				

Table No.7 Accuracy data of IMP-A, IMP-B and IMP-C of TAZ

Component		LOQ	50%	100%	150%
Imp-A	Concentration $\mu\text{g/mL}$	0.02	0.25	0.5	0.75
	#Mean Accuracy %	103.0	97.7	98.0	98.1
Imp-B	Concentration $\mu\text{g/mL}$	0.01	1.5	3.0	4.5
	#Mean Accuracy %	100.2	96.8	98.0	99.5
Imp-C	Concentration $\mu\text{g/mL}$	0.01	0.25	0.5	0.75
	#Mean Accuracy %	97.7	103.7	104.5	100.3
#... Average of three determinations					

Table No.8 Solution stability results of TAZ

Duration	Imp-A %	Imp-B %	Imp-C %	Total Impurities %
Initial	0.32	0.31	0.32	0.95
24 hrs.	0.33	0.32	0.32	0.97
72 hrs.	0.32	0.33	0.32	0.97

The forced degradation of TAZ topical formulation was carried out as per ICH guideline¹⁴. All stress conditions and obtained results are shown in Table 2. The purity angle was less than purity threshold for all the stress conditions. Interference was not observed from blank and placebo preparations. Blank, placebo, control sample and impurity spiked sample chromatograms are presented in figure 5. Stress study samples are presented in Figure 6.

LOD, LOQ and RRF establishment:

LOD and LOQ were established by linearity method. Linearity was performed with a range of 0.01 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ to 1.0 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ concentration. The correlation co-efficient value was found to be more than 0.99 [Table 3]. Relative response factor (RRF) was calculated for each known impurities by taking the ratio of impurity slope to Tazarotene slope^{15,16}.

Figure No.5 The chromatogram of (a) blank (b) placebo (c) control sample and (d) Impurity spiked sample for precision

Linearity:

Linearity was performed for imp-A, Imp-B, Imp-C and TAZ. The correlation coefficient value was found to be more than 0.999 [Table 4]. Bias was less than 2.0% for each case.

Figure No.6 The chromatogram of (a) acid degradation sample (b) base degradation sample (c) peroxide degradation sample (d) photolytic light exposed sample.

Method Precision at LOQ:

The precision of the test method at LOQ was conducted by injecting six placebo solution preparations spiked with each of known impurities (Imp-A, B and C) at LOQ concentration, calculated % of individual Impurity and total Impurities, % RSD from the six preparations are summarized in Table 5.

Method Precision:

The method was found to be precise with six sample preparations by spiking the impurities at 0.3% level [Table 6]. The % RSD of Imp-A, B, C in six sample preparation was found to be less than 6.0%.

Accuracy:

Accuracy was established by recovery methodology by spiking each of imp-A, B, C, at six different levels, in triplicate preparations, starting from LOQ to 150% of impurity specification of drug product [Table 7]. The recovery results for all impurities were found to be between 90-110%.

Solution stability:

The solution stability of the standard and spiked sample preparation in diluent was studied for 72 hrs. at bench top. The solution under study was compared with freshly prepared standard solution. The samples solution stability was established upto 72 hrs and found satisfactory [Table 8].

Robustness:

The robustness was demonstrated by varying; flow rate, mobile phase buffer pH and column oven temperature [Table 1]. The method was found to be robust with respect to flow rate, pH and column temperature without any significant changes in system suitability parameters and relative retention time of impurities in sample.

CONCLUSION

A stability indicating RP-HPLC method was successfully developed for determination of related impurities in TAZ gel and validated according to ICH guidelines. Established RRT and RRF values for known impurities can be useful to determine the related impurities in TAZ gel using TAZ standard only. An explained approach for diluent selection with consideration of drug-diluent chemical compatibility would be an added tool for LC method developer. Low cost, environment friendly and satisfactory LOD, LOQ, precision and accuracy are the main features of this method. The method was critically validated and statistically generated high quality data proves that the method is linear, sensitive, selective, specific and robust. This method can be applied for analytical development laboratory during product development, product stability testing and in quality control laboratory.

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